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**Investigating the Effectiveness of Compassion-based Therapy on the
amount of Rumination and Depression Symptoms in Women between 20
and 30 years old**

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Abstract

The aim of the present study was to determine the effectiveness of compassion-based therapy on the rate of rumination and depression symptoms of women aged 20 to 30, in which semi-experimental method with a pre-test-post-test design with a control group was used. The statistical population in this research was made up of all women with symptoms of rumination and depression in Tabriz who referred to Razi Hospital in Tabriz in 1402. After obtaining the necessary permission to select a sample from the available sampling method, 30 people were selected. To determine the effectiveness, Gilbert (2010) treatment protocol was used, which was implemented as a group for 8 sessions of 90 minutes. To measure rumination, Nolen Hoeksma and Morrow's Rumination Response Styles Questionnaire (1991) and to measure depression symptoms from Beck's Depression Questionnaire (1996), as a pre-test and after the treatment as a post-test were used. Finally, after collecting the data, the methods of descriptive statistics, mean and standard deviation, and inferential statistics of univariate covariance analysis were used. The significance level was considered 0.05 in all tests. The findings showed that there was a significant difference between the control and experimental groups in both rumination variables ($p < 0.001$) and depression symptoms ($p < 0.001$). According to the results obtained from this research, the treatment based on compassion can greatly help to reduce rumination and depression symptoms of depressed women.

Keywords: *Compassion-based Therapy, Rumination, Depression Symptoms.*

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Introduction:

Gender differences do often reported on the rate of depression in the literature; by the beginning of childhood period, the risk of getting depression in women is two times more than men. To illustrate gender differences in depression several psychological, social and biological explanations have been presented. The context reasons included hormone changes especially related to menstruation, pregnancy and menopause cycle, social standards and expectations, balancing job and family responsibilities, gender discrimination and confrontation with based gender violence. In this regard, rumination is also one of the issues related repeated depression in women (Hosgoren & Hasanli, 2023).

Rumination is considered as repeated, long and lasting thoughts about oneself, feelings, personal worries and distressing experiences (Stelmach-Lask et al., 2024). Rumination is a component that has main role in depression disorders and leads to lasting and intensifying the disorder symptoms and it would cause other psychological disorders to emerge. Different researches showed that tendency to think about the past mistakes and failures do probably has role in the emergence being involved in rumination of depression disorder (Smith et al., 2021). Rumination is a negative mental habit which leads to the individuals' concentration on the problems and emergence of distress symptoms and this state intensifies negative feelings (Scaini et al., 2021).

Depression is a complicated and pervasive psychological disorder that influences millions of people all over the world (James et al., 2018). This disorder is being recognized with a spectrum of behavioral symptoms like lasting sorrow feeling, hopelessness, valueless and lack of interest or joy to routine activities. These symptoms are often accompanied with concentration problems, change in appetite, sleep disorders-insomnia or oversleeping and taking action to suicide (Liu et al., 2024). Other symptoms included depressive moods, losing interest to routine activities. If depression be long lasting, it would be involved in routine life and in some cases, it may even lead to suicide thoughts or real suicide (World Health Organization, 2017). Usual therapies for depression and its comorbid disorders are pharmaceuticals like anti-depressives pharmaceuticals.

Use of anti-depressives pharmaceuticals, besides their positive effects have negative side effects like drop in blood pressure, constipation, decreased sexual function, digestive symptoms, weight gain and metabolic abnormalities (Saha et al., 2021; Pillinger et al., 2023). Considering the disadvantages and alternative outcomes, it seems that non-pharmaceutics therapies like psychotherapy has precedence on pharmaceuticals therapy and several researches do also confirmed that the effectiveness of psychotherapy including cognitive-behavioral therapy (Li et al., 2020), mindfulness based therapy (Fumero et al., 2020) and dialectical behavioral therapy (Saito et al., 2020) on decreased depression. Besides these therapies, one of the other therapeutic approaches that is considered to improve depression and rumination symptoms is compassion-based therapy (Agalar & Akrami, 2022).

Compassion-based therapy was formulated in response to this observation that in many people especially those who have high shame and self-criticism, they had some difficulties in making kind and self-supporting inner voices while receiving traditional therapies. The basic principles in compassion-based therapy points to this issue that the external soothing thoughts, factors, images, and behaviors should be internal and in this case, the human's mind gets calm in front of these internal factors like it shows reaction to the external factors (Millard et al., 2023). Two main purpose of this approach are decreased self-oriented violence and increased one's abilities in order to make the sense of self-confidence, kindness and self-soothing that could operate as antitoxin against feeling of being threatening. The main activities of this therapy is to make the capability of compassionate (Joe et al., 2019). The present similar research indicate the efficacy of compassion-based therapy on rumination (Khadri et al., 2022; Frostadottir et al., 2019) and depression (Soltanidelgosha et al., 2023; Asano et al., 2022).

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With regard to what was taken from the literature, compassion-based therapy leads to decreased depression and rumination by improving kindness and accepting pains and suffer instead of self-criticizing and self-judging; however, this issue is important that this therapy has not been performed on women aged 20 to 30, yet; therefore, the present study was carried out by the purpose of determining the effectiveness of compassion-based therapy on the rate of rumination and depression symptoms of women aged 20 to 30 and this question is proposed that whether the compassion-based therapy would be effective on the rate of rumination and depression symptoms of women aged 20 to 30?

Review of the theoretical bases and related literature

Compassion-based therapy: Gilbert who developed compassion-based therapy, defines compassion as sensitivity to one's and the others' sufferings (involvement) by commitment to try to decrease and prevent them (Gilbert, 2014). This therapy is based on the principles which originate from evolutionary, social, developmental psychology, neuroscience, and emotional patterns (Rahmani et al, 2020).

Rumination: Rumination is recognized as ever occupation to a thought or subject and thinking to it and is a class of conscious thoughts that are revolve around an axis and are repeated without dependency to the environmental demands. Rumination could lead to increased negative mood effects on problem solving and motivation. Also, this issue makes the people thoughts' orientation negative and weakens their ability to problem solving (Heidarian et al, 2016).

Depression: depression disorder is a serious mental disorder in the world. It is evident that depression disorder has negative effects on the individual's feelings, thought and behavior. It could lead to several physical and mental problems like feeling of sorrow, obesity, loss of interest, sleep, movement slowness, purposeless physical activities and suicide thoughts (American psychiatric association, 2022).

Soltanidelgosha et al (2023) in their research with the title of "effectiveness of compassion-based therapy on depression, anxiety and aggression of medical emergency staffs during Crona" showed that compassion-based therapy is effective on decreased depression, anxiety and aggression.

Khadri et al (2022) in their research with the title of "effectiveness of training compassion based mindfulness on decreased rumination and perceived stress in adolescent girls" showed that training compassion based mindfulness is effective on decreased rumination and perceived stress.

Asano et al (2022) do also in a study under the title of "Benefits of group compassion-focused therapy for treatment-resistant depression: A pilot randomized controlled trial" showed that group compassion-focused therapy is effective on treatment-resistant depression.

Also, Frostadottir et al., (2019) in a research with the title of "effects of mindfulness based cognitive therapy (MBCT) and compassion focused therapy (CFT) on symptom change, mindfulness, self-compassion, and rumination in clients with depression, anxiety, and stress" indicated that mindfulness based cognitive therapy (MBCT) and compassion focused therapy (CFT) are effective on symptom change, mindfulness, self-compassion, and rumination in clients with depression, anxiety, and stress.

Methodology

The methodology of the present research was semi-experimental method with a pre-test-post-test design with a control group by randomized assignment of the subject groups. The statistical population in this research was made up of all women with symptoms of rumination and depression in Tabriz in 1402. The sample group were included those women referring to Razi Hospital in Tabriz in 1402. Using available sampling method, and after obtaining the

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permission of the hospital officials and the referees, the Questionnaires of Nolen Hoeksma and Morrow's Rumination Response Styles (1991) and Beck's Depression Questionnaire (1996) were performed among them and among those who obtained 1 standard deviation higher than mean, 30 people were selected considering the entry criteria included: 1) age (20 to 30), 2) gender (female), 3) being single, 4) being employed; and exclusion criteria like: 1) having serious illnesses like cancer and MS, 2) receiving consulting and personal and group psychological sessions simultaneously with the present research, 3) use of psychiatric pharmaceuticals like anti-depressives and sedative medicines, 4) being absent for more than one session in the therapeutic sessions and they were divided randomly into two experimental (15 people) and control groups (15 people). 15 people were calculated for each group based on the software of determining the sample volume, Power G3 and considering the following parameters (Motamedi & Zamani, 2017). Effect size= .36; Alpha coefficient= .05; test power=.68; Repetitions= 2; λ Noncentrality parameter=4.179; critical F=3.767; Numerator df= 2; Denominator df=29; Actual power=.81; Pillai V=.25.

- a) Hoeksema and Morrow's rumination questionnaire: the scale of rumination Response Styles is subscale of Hoeksema and Morrow's rumination questionnaire. This scale has been formulated by Hoeksema and Morrow (1991) that has 22 items and its items are scored based on 4 degree Likert spectrum from 1 (almost never) to 4 (almost always). The least score obtained in this this scale is 22 and the highest score is 88 and the highest score indicate more rumination. Besides, it included three subscales of distraction, reflection and overthinking (Kazemi et al, 2020). Based on the empirical observations, rumination Response Styles scale has high internal reliability. Cronbach alpha coefficient is in the domain of .88 to .92. Retest correlation of this questionnaire is .67 in several researches and its inter-class correlation was measured 5 times and was reported as .75. Wells & Fisher (2015) reported alpha coefficient of this scale as .90 and its retest reliability as .67. In a study by Bagerinezhad et al (2010), this questionnaire reliability coefficient by Cronbach alpha was obtained as .90, .89 and .88. The validity of this questionnaire was reported through its correlation with mindfulness beliefs as .65 in the level of .001 that shows its high validity (Kazemi et al, 2020).
- b) Beck depression questionnaire (BDI-II): This questionnaire was introduced in 1961 by Beck et al and was published in 1987. In 1996, this questionnaire was revised. This scale has 21 items that deals with the symptoms of the person's depression during last two weeks. The score domain for each item is from zero to three (zero indicates lack of symptoms of depression and high scores indicate more severe levels of depression). The determined cut points for this scale included 0 to 13 (sadness), 14 to 19 (light depression); 20 to 28 (average depression); and 29 to 63 (severe depression). Beck et al (1996) reported retest reliability of this scale after one week retest as .93. Also, correlation coefficient of BDI-II was reported with Hamilton depression scale as .71. Generally, BDI-II was identified as a valid and reliable instruments to recognize and measure depression severity all over the world and in the researches and studies, it has so many applies. Validity and reliability of this scale were examined in several researches in the Iranian society. The internal reliability of this scale regarding Cronbach alpha coefficient was reported as .73 to .92 and retest coefficient as .48 to .86 (Yarveysi et al, 2021).

Therapeutic sessions were held by a consultant with Ph.D. degree in counselling and a psychologist by degree of M.A. in a private counselling center in Tabriz city. The group members were asked not to talk about the sessions' content during the therapy procedure in order to prevent information transfer. After the end of sessions, post – test were taken from the members. In order to prevent the group members drop, during the initial interview with each one of them, the members were asked to keep their commitment to participate in all the

sessions, this was observed during the sessions and the group correlation that was made among the members, prevent the group members' drop. The group members received group compassion - based therapy for 8, 1.5 hour sessions (2 months) based on Gilbert protocol (2010), but the control group received no therapy. After the end of therapeutic sessions and one month after performing post-test, both groups (the experimental and control) were examined using measurement instruments, too. This task (performing post-test and follow-up) was carried out because of examining the efficacy compassion - based therapy (independent variable) on rumination and depression (dependent variable). Also, it should be mentioned that the control group members received group compassion - based therapy for 8, 1.5 hour sessions (2 months).

Table 1: *Content of Compassion - Based Therapy Protocol*

session	Session title	Session content
1	Introduction of group members, explanation of how mental function works and effects of disorder on its function	Indicating the group principles, explanation of affect failure symptoms, its outcomes on psychological capitals and its dimensions, members conversation related to affect failure experience, explanation of how mental function works and how and why disorder in its function happens.
2	Definition of compassionate	Explanation of compassionate, what is compassionate and how could be overcome on it?
3	Thinking about compassionate	Thinking about compassionate toward others, focus and concentration on compassionate, compassionate thinking, compassionate behavior, compassionate imagination
4	Increasing energy, acceptance and not to judge	Increasing kindness and energy, mindfulness, acceptance, thought and power, kindness and not to judge
5	Exercise of consciousness, its advantages and disadvantages	Exercise of mindfulness consciousness, examining beliefs that are accompanied with useless emotions, their advantages and disadvantages
6	Performing Compassionate exercise	Exercising compassionate color, compassionate voice and image, letter writing based on compassionate
7	Exercise of anger, Exercise of fear, getting ready to end of the group	Compassionate letter writing, Exercise of anger and Compassionate, Exercise of fear and Compassionate, getting ready to end of the group
8	The end of sessions	Review, conclusion, and end of the group work

Findings

The sample of the present research included two groups of women with 15 people. The mean and standard deviation of total participants' age was 25.23 ± 3.266 . Homogeneity of the subjects in the variables was examined through two independent group t-test. There was no

significant difference between the participants' age in both the experimental and control groups ($p < .005$).

Table 2: *The Mean and Standard Deviation of the Research Subjects' Age (Each Group No=15)*

Variable	group	mean ± standard deviation	statistic	Level of significance
Age	Experimental	25.3±27.127	T=-0.055	.957
	control	25.3±20.509		
	total	25.3±23.266		

Two independent group t-test* significant difference, $p < .05$.

Table 3 shows mean and standard deviation of rumination and depression symptoms. Based on the findings of table 3, there is difference between the scores of the variables of rumination and depression symptoms in the experimental group in post-test stage in comparison to pre-test after performing the intervention.

Table 3: *Descriptive Data of the Variables of Rumination and Depression Symptoms Separated to the Tests Groups*

variables	group	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean	standard deviation	mean	standard deviation
rumination	Experimental	60.93	10.089	51.60	6.712
	control	59.33	13.668	62.67	12.328
	total	60..13	11.831	57.135	9.52
Depression sypmtoms	Experimental	33.30	12.269	21.19	6.590
	Control	35.40	12.970	38.42	14.205
	total	34.35	12.619	29.805	10.397

In the examination of pre-assumptions of one variate analysis of covariance test, examination of pre-assumptions of the variables linearity by Q-Q graph for rumination and depression symptoms variables showed that assumption of linearity relation was not overtaken. Also, test of Shapiro-Wilk showed that pre-assumptions of the studied variables distribution normality in the examined sample was fulfilled; because the calculated z-values in the level of $p > .05$ for each variable are not significant. The results of Leven test indicates equality of variance matrices for rumination was $p = .108$ and for depression symptoms $p = .231$. In the examination of homogeneity of regression slope, the obtained values between dispersion and rumination ($F = .028$, $p > .870$) and depression symptoms variables ($F = 3.239$, $p > .084$), the results indicates fulfilment of homogeneity of regression pre-assumption.

Table 4: *Test of Analysis of Covariance to Examine Interaction Between Dispersion and Independent Variable*

variable	effect	Sum of squares	Df	Mean of squares	F	Level of significance
rumination	Group*pre-tests	2.428	1	2.428	.028	.870
depression symptoms	Group*pre-tests	172.571	1	172.571	3.239	.084

After confirmation of all the assumptions, in order to compare the mean scores of rumination and depression symptoms of the groups in post-test, ANCOVA was used. Such that pre-test scores were controlled as dispersion variable and then post-test scores were compared. In order to compare mean scores of post – test of rumination and depression symptoms, after controlling the effect of pre-test, ANCOVA test was used that results are presented in table 5.

Table 5: *Test of Analysis of Covariance to Examine Mean Scores of Post-Test in the Groups*

variable	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	F	Level of significance	Etha squire
rumination	2195.046	1	2195.046	25.806	.001	.489
depression symptoms	2534.975	1	2534.975	43.933	.001	.619

The obtained results in the first section in table 5 shows that after balancing pre-test scores, there was difference between two groups (Experimental and control groups) in post-test of rumination ($F=25.806$; $P=.001$). This indicates the effectiveness of compassion - based therapy on depressed women rumination. Also, the obtained effect coefficient shows that .49 of the groups differences in rumination scores in post-test relates to the effect of compassion - based therapy. In this regard, the first hypothesis of the research is confirmed. Also, the obtained results in second section of table 5 shows that after modification of pre-test scores, there was significant difference between both groups (Experimental and control groups) in post-test of depression symptoms ($F=43.933$, $P=.001$). In this regard, the second hypothesis of the research is confirmed, too.

Discussion and Conclusion

The present research was carried out by the purpose of examining the effectiveness of compassion-based therapy on the rate of rumination and depression symptoms of women aged 20 to 30; the results obtained from the analyses indicated the effect of this therapy on improvement of these variables and points to its significant effectiveness on decreased rumination and depression symptoms in these women. The present research results is consistent with Khadri et al (2022); Frostadottir et al (2019); Soltanielgoshia et al (2023) and Asano et al (2022).

In the explanation of effectiveness of compassion-based therapy on rumination and depression symptoms of depressed women, it could be said that rumination as a coping strategy may be an instrument to escape unwanted situation that increases negative mood and in long term, it could lead to mental distress and punishment behavior and would have main role in adjustment with disorder (Daughters et al., 2017). It is not far - fetched that people with high self-compassion in confronting with hard and limited situations, behave kindly with themselves and instead of rumination and being drown in these thoughts, they look at this phenomenon with much mindfulness. Learning the proposed techniques in the sessions of compassion therapy leads to prevent repeated thoughts that cause review of the past memories and problems far from their minds and not to overthink about several issues. Also, performing this protocol is effective taking away these unwanted thoughts in these people and decreases repeating their past actions and speeches and provide a bed to confront with life realities and also thoughts and feelings and routine issues acceptingly, and without judgment and also broad-mindedness (Neff & Pommier, 2013). Accepting the thoughts and emotions and phenomena such that they occur in the present moment, not in the way they are passed under our mental filter, gives a client a perception above judgment framework and classification of critic and actor mind, a

perception in the accepting conscious width that only reminds the person to be in the moment and control their passing thought and emotions and by efficient and calmer performance, solve their problems (Neff & Dahm, 2015).

In the explanation of effectiveness of compassion-based therapy on depression symptoms of depressed women, it could be said that compassion is a powerful cognitive component and is under the influence of the person's trends toward oneself and others. Therefore, regarding that this cognitive theory that depression is accompanied with the thoughts and cognitions related to loss and frustration and negative trends to oneself, others, past and future, it could propose that there is relationship among these properties and depression; the more there be negative self-concept and self-criticism, the more depression symptoms. In compassion-based therapy, the clients learn compassion skills and characteristics. Training compassion mind helps the clients to change their problematic cognitive and emotional patterns. The main effective area in compassion-based therapy is the people self-criticism (Agalar & Akrami, 2022). Compassion-based therapy exercises like imagination the safe place and mindfulness lead to increased soothing system and as a result provide the ground to evolve and change these patients and provide their tolerance threshold. Increased compassion leads to the weak people accept his past and present failure and problems and increase his attempts to change and compensate his weaknesses that by themselves lead to decreased depression (Ahmadi, et al, 2019).

This research faced with some limitations like any other studies; this study was carried out in the population limited to women aged 20 to 30 lining in Tabriz, so generation of the findings to other groups should be by caution. By considering theoretical and empirical background of the present research, and regarding the statistical population of this research, it is suggested that this study be carried out among different statistical population and other cities; In the future research, by paying attention to gender, the intended variables be examined.

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